

THE FLOW BEHAVIOUR OF COMPOSITES CONTAINING CUT, ALIGNED FIBRES

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SUMMARY: The possibility of improving the formability of aligned fibre composites by cutting the fibres into controlled lengths using a laser has been investigated. It is shown that the ease with which the composite may be deformed in tension is substantially improved. It is found that the composite deforms primarily by the growth of the slots introduced by the laser cutting process and that the way in which this growth occurs is dependent upon the details of the slot pattern.

KEYWORDS: formability, processing, aligned fibres

INTRODUCTION

Long fibre thermoplastic composites can be formed using relatively low cost techniques such as diaphragm forming [1], rubber forming [2], and stamp forming [3]. However, in more complex shapes, such as those requiring a reverse or double curvature, fibre wrinkling, component buckling [1,3,4] and thickness variations [1,5] often occur during the forming process, particularly at high forming rates.

The occurrence of these features is principally associated with the inextensible nature of the fibres [6-8] restricting tensile flow in the direction of the fibres [9]. Under compression the fibres can buckle and become misaligned [3,9]. In a component such as a U-channel the strains on one face of the laminate are different to those on the opposing face so that shear is required between the individual plies, normally taking place within resin rich areas between the individual lamina. However, with a reverse or double curvature, such as a hemisphere, additional shearing between the individual fibres must also take place within a single ply [10]. While this allows the laminate to conform to the specimen geometry these processes often result in undesirable thickness variations in the component [1,5].

The superior properties of long fibre composites require not only long fibres but also that the fibres are aligned along the tensile axis. Misalignments of only a few degrees can cause a substantial reduction in the properties. It is more difficult to try to align discontinuous fibres, for instance by extrusion, than it is to cut aligned continuous fibres in the form of pre-preg, so allowing tensile deformation in the direction of the fibres. A number of methods for doing this have been tried [8,10]. In this study the flow behaviour and formability of a thermoplastic polymer containing uniaxially aligned carbon fibres cut into shorter lengths using a laser has been investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Fibre Cutting

The material used was a poly (ether ether ketone) containing a volume fraction of 0.61 of continuous and uniaxially aligned carbon fibres (ICI plc, APC-2). The fibres were cut into controlled lengths by moving a sheet of the prepreg material below a laser, giving a pattern of elongated holes. The geometry of these could be varied by changing the rate at which the material was moved, the length of time for which the laser was on and the interval between successive firings of the laser [11].

The main features of the geometry of the hole array are shown in Fig. 1(a). The material is cut into strips each with a length l , in this case either 20 or 50 mm and with a width, D , approximately equal to the length of the slot formed by the laser, typically $160\ \mu\text{m}$. The adjacent strip is similarly cut except that the slot is displaced by a distance P_y in the direction of the fibres. After a number of strips have been cut, the position of the slot is level with the original slot, the distance between the two being P_x . The very small offset between the holes on the diagonal line gives the appearance of lines of slots a distance P_x apart in the transverse direction, and P_y apart in the direction parallel to the fibres, as shown in Fig. 1(b).

Fig. 1: Showing (a) a schematic arrangement of the laser cut slots. Note that the material is made up essentially of relatively long strips of fibres, each strip of width, D . (b) shows the appearance of an actual array. Note that it appears to be a rectangular array of slots.

The pattern must also ensure that all the fibres are cut. To minimise the possibility of any continuous fibres remaining due to any fibre misalignment, there is an overlap between the holes, δ . The slots do not have a uniform size through the thickness of the prepreg as the laser energy is absorbed by the material, so the mean diameter of the hole on the surface of the prepreg on which the laser is incident is typically twice that on the lower surface [12].

Specimen Production

Strips of the pre-prep 420 mm long and 75 mm wide were perforated in the gauge section of each sample. Samples with mean fibre lengths of 20 and 50 mm were made, with perforated gauge lengths of 40 and 100 mm respectively.

The perforated strips of pre-preg were butt-jointed together using a soldering iron to give plies with typical dimensions of 450 x 420 mm. 8-ply laminates were consolidated in an autoclave heated to 380°C at a pressure of 1.05 MPa for 20 minutes. The plies in the laminate were stacked with the pre-preg surfaces on which the laser was first incident, uppermost, taking care to ensure that the holes in neighbouring plies did not overlap.

Mechanical Testing

Tensile drawing was carried out on a 10 kN servo-hydraulic machine at strain-rates between 4.2×10^{-4} and $4.2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Tests were carried out on both continuous and laser cut material. Tensile drawing tests were carried out at temperatures of 380°C and 340°C using a radiant bulb furnace with six quartz iodine infra-red lamps fitted within a water cooled stainless steel case giving a uniform heated length on the sample of approximately 110 mm.

To study the overall tensile flow behaviour of the composite and its variation with fibre length some samples were strained to failure. Some samples were deformed to smaller strains to investigate any microstructural changes occurring during straining.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Flow Behaviour

Typical stress/strain curves for samples containing 20 mm long fibres and 50 mm fibres drawn at 380°C at strain-rates between 4.16×10^{-4} and $4.16 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ are shown in Fig. 2(a) and (b) respectively. It can be seen that the stress rises approximately linearly with increasing strain until some peak stress is reached, after which the stress falls. This is consistent with tensile drawing experiments carried out elsewhere on materials containing aligned fibres cut into shorter lengths, but by different methods to that used here [8,13]. Reducing the strain-rate decreased the magnitude of this peak stress. Similar behaviour was observed at 340°C. However, the peak stresses were higher than those at 380°C at equivalent strain rates.

Fig. 2: Showing the variation in flow stress with strain-rate for the composite containing fibres with a mean length of (a) 20 mm, and (b) 50 mm, drawn at 380 °C.

The tensile drawing behaviour of the continuous fibre material is shown in Fig. 3. The stress rises rapidly to a peak at approximately 800 MPa, at which point the fibres break. At high strain-rates the stress immediately drops to zero but at lower rates the broken fibres are held in the matrix and the composite can be drawn to a limited extent. However, the peak stress in the unperforated composite is more than twenty times higher than that observed in the perforated material.

Fig. 3: Showing the variation in flow stress for the composite containing continuous fibres drawn at 380 °C.

The flow behaviour of a Newtonian viscous fluid containing a given volume fraction of discontinuous fibres, V_f has been considered by Byron-Pipes *et al* [7]. Using a shear-lag approach, they showed that the applied stress, σ_y , at the point where the stress in the matrix is equal to the shear yield stress, τ_y , would be given by

$$\sigma_y = \frac{l}{d} \tau_y V_f \quad (1)$$

where l and d are the mean length and the diameter of the fibres respectively and V_f is the volume fraction of the fibres.

To compare these ideas with the observations here, the shear yield stress of the unreinforced resin at 380°C was measured by capillary rheometry. The values obtained at the equivalent tensile strain-rates to those used in the experiments are given in Table 1, together with the corresponding peak stresses for the materials containing 20 and 50 mm fibres. Setting V_f to 0.61, d to 7 μm and l to either 20 or 50 mm, as appropriate, allows the values for the tensile yield stress to be calculated from Equation (1) for the different materials. From Fig. 4, it can be seen that the predictions give good agreement with the experimental observations, suggesting that at the peak stress the material is essentially behaving as a uniform array of discontinuous fibres, in which the interfacial shear stresses are just approaching the flow stress of the polymer, allowing uniform flow to occur.

Table 1: Showing the stress required to give flow of poly (ether ether ketone) at different strain-rates.

Tensile strain-rate (s ⁻¹)	Polymer flow stress (Pa)
4.16 10 ⁻²	3652
4.16 10 ⁻³	1386
4.16 10 ⁻⁴	526

Fig. 4: Showing the predictions of Equation 1 compared with the experimental results for composites containing fibres with a mean length of (a) 20 mm and (b) 50 mm.

The decrease in the flow stress in Fig. 2, has been observed elsewhere and was attributed to local thinning occurring in the sample followed by eventual tearing and failure [8]. Examination of the samples after testing showed that there was rarely any observable macroscopic necking, although after strains of typically 0.04 the fibres did tend to come loose from the sample. The flow stress however had already substantially decreased in all cases.

However, as can be seen in Figs 5(a) and (b), it was clear that large voids had opened up in the sample. It was unambiguously established that these holes had grown from those introduced by the laser cutting process because the fibres at the surfaces of the holes had swollen ends, which are a characteristic of the laser perforation process [12, 14].

Fig. 5(a) shows a sample deformed to a strain below that at which the peak stress was reached and it can be seen that the perforations have all strained uniformly. However at a strain just above that where the peak stress is reached, Fig. 5(b), it can be seen that the holes begin to grow at different rates. Both micrographs have been taken from the surfaces of the specimens and have not in this case been filled with resin. Clearly the presence of a normal pressure might be expected to force resin into the holes. However given that the holes were filled with resin before tensile drawing, it is unlikely that it should prevent this growth. This has been confirmed [8] by similar observations in materials that have been diaphragm formed. Clearly these holes are likely to have deleterious effects on the mechanical properties of formed material.

Fig. 5: Showing the holes growing in a sample containing fibres with a mean length of 50mm, deformed at 340 °C to a strain (a) just below that at which the peak stress is reached and (b) just above that at which the peak stress is reached.

One way in which such voids can grow is by the shear of adjacent strips of fibres each of width D , as shown in Fig. 1(a), past one another, so that all the deformation is concentrated in a very narrow region between the strips. If this were the case, it would be expected that the overall displacement of the sample would be equal to the extension of the laser cut slots in a strip of the sample with a width of the slot. Each sample containing 50 mm fibres had twenty-three rows of perforations along the gauge length, each a distance P_y apart (for 20 mm material there were twenty-one rows of perforations). Bearing in mind that the mean fibre length is half the gauge length, each strip of fibres in the 50 mm material covers twelve rows of holes, each row a distance P_y apart, before another hole cuts that strip. This means that if the sample displacement is due entirely to the growth of the holes, it should be equal to the displacement measured from two sets of holes, each twelve rows apart (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6: Schematic of a sample showing the rows of laser cut slots for a mean fibre length of 50 mm.

For both sets of specimens the average hole size per line was measured and added to the corresponding average hole size twelve rows along. It was assumed that the groups of fibres between the respective row of perforations were all moving as one unit. Table 2(a) and (b)

show the net opening of the holes for each of the rows as numbered in Fig. 6 for specimens strained to just below and just above the peak stress respectively and the row numbers that correspond to the end of a given strip of fibres.

Table 2(a): Sum of hole openings for samples strained to just below the peak stress.

Row No.	1,12,23	2,13	3,14	4,15	5,16	6,17	7,18	8,19	9,20	10,21	11,22	Mean
Hole opening (mm)	0.44	0.52	0.56	0.52	0.50	0.46	0.49	0.47	0.57	0.52	0.48	0.50

Table 2(b): Sum of hole openings for samples strained to just above the peak stress.

Row No.	1,12,23	2,13	3,14	4,15	5,16	6,17	7,18	8,19	9,20	10,21	11,22	Mean
Hole opening (mm)	2.27	2.45	2.64	2.75	2.91	2.74	2.47	2.73	2.63	2.42	2.45	2.59

The total displacement for the sample strained to just below the peak stress was 0.95 mm, approximately double that measured from the elongation of the holes, if this were caused by shear between the adjacent strips of cut fibres. For the sample strained to above the peak stress, the total displacement was 3.4 mm, whereas that measured from the elongation of the holes was 2.6 mm. Clearly once the peak stress has been reached, the majority of the displacement is caused by shear in very narrow regions between the adjacent strips of fibres. The decreasing flow stress might then be interpreted in terms of some shear thinning effect. This is entirely consistent with the idea that flow occurs once the shear stress of the matrix has reached its flow stress. Indeed one might expect that flow could occur nowhere else apart from within these thin zones between the strips.

However the observation that substantial hole growth can occur before the peak stress shows that not only is there another way in which the specimen can irreversibly deform, but also that there is another mechanism by which the holes can grow. So far we have assumed that the body is made up simply of cut strips of fibres stuck together. However this neglects the overlap region which was introduced to minimise the possibility of any intact fibres remaining.

The existence of the overlap region introduces a zone between laser cut slots in adjacent strips of material, marked in Fig. 7(a) as ABCD. These zones exist right across the width of the material, so that deformation of the material within these zones gives rise to a macroscopic deformation of the sample, as shown in Fig. 7(b). Such a deformation would be expected to give rise to holes which have grown at an angle to the tensile axis, as shown in Fig. 7(b) and this was observed, as shown in Fig. 8.

The experimental observations suggest that this mode of deformation predominates at lower applied stresses, before the peak stress is reached. The initial length of these fibres is given by P_y in Fig. 1(a). In both cases, this is about 0.1 that of the mean fibre length. Using equation 1, the yield stress of the regions due to the overlap is less than that elsewhere in the

material by a factor of 10, so that flow of these regions would be predicted to occur before that of the surrounding material, consistent with the observations.

Fig. 7: Showing an array of holes containing an overlap to minimise the possibility of any fibres remaining uncut. This introduces regions such as that marked ABCD in (a) which can deform to A'B'C'D' without any deformation of the immediately surrounding material, as shown in (b). Compare this with Fig. 8.

Fig. 8: Showing elongated holes which appear to have deformed in a manner similar to that in Fig. 7(b).

Both mechanisms give rise to hole elongation. The difference between the two is that where the overlap region is unimportant, the total displacement due to hole elongation is obtained by summing the contribution from every twelfth row of holes (in this case). Where hole overlap is important, the displacement will need to be summed from every row of holes, see Fig. 6. Of course the relative contribution from the two mechanisms cannot be simply separated and more detailed measurements are now underway to investigate this further.

CONCLUSIONS

Tensile drawing experiments on a thermoplastic polymer containing 61% of carbon fibres by volume has demonstrated that the laser cutting approach allows the material to be drawn in tension much more easily than material containing continuous fibres. The magnitudes of the stresses required to draw the cut fibre material are close to those predicted for a fluid containing a given volume fraction of discontinuous fibres. It has been shown that deformation of the sample can occur in two ways. At lower stresses this occurs by the deformation of zones between the laser drilled slots. After the peak stress, this occurs predominantly by the movement of adjacent strips of material, whose thickness is equal to the length of a laser drilled slot. Both processes result in the formation of large elongated voids.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work forms part of a project involving Integrated Materials Technology, T&N Technology, DRA Farnborough and the University of Cambridge. Thanks are due to T&N Technology for financial support for one of us (DTS).

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